

CODEN [USA]: IAJPBB

ISSN: 2349-7750

**INDO AMERICAN JOURNAL OF
PHARMACEUTICAL SCIENCES**Available online at: <http://www.iajps.com>

Research Article

DEFENSE MECHANISMS, STARTLE, SURPRISE AND COPING¹Dr Muhammad Saqib Rabbani, ²Dr. Samreen Asif¹BDS, MPhil. Senior Registrar, Avicena Medical College Lahore, ²PG Trainee, MD Psychiatry, Sir Ganga Ram Hospital Lahore.**Article Received:** May 2019**Accepted:** June 2019**Published:** July 2019**Abstract:**

The defense mechanisms preference of the participants those were bound to attend their workplace on time was studied in two situations. Startle was generated by a stranger professional who asked participants about 'reaching the office late' whereas surprise was created by asking participants about 'always attending the office in time'. It was assumed that divergent respondents to cope would prefer heterogeneous defense mechanisms; however, a limited number of defense mechanisms were engrossed, 'collective coping' for situation influences discussed. More studies would further clarify.

Keywords: *Defense Mechanisms, Startle, Surprise, Coping, Situation Influences, Collective Coping.***Corresponding author:**¹Dr Muhammad Saqib Rabbani

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Please cite this article in press Muhammad Saqib Rabbani et al., *Defense Mechanisms, Startle, Surprise And Coping.*, Indo Am. J. P. Sci, 2019; 07(07).

INTRODUCTION:

Adaptation is an essential human survival requirement. Defense mechanisms are an important human coping adaptation strategy (Jamilian, Zamani, Darvishi & Khansari, 2014), however, much less has been researched and agreed upon in this area and much more is required to be explored (Vaillant 2012). Present work explored the influence of demographic factors in the selection of defense mechanisms by the participants to cope with generated startle and surprise? However, findings instead of heterogeneity of defense mechanisms choice depicted noticeable uniformity that was argued as collective coping, perhaps because of the situation related group reasons?

Mechanisms of defense are an important and sustaining construct in psychoanalysis since the publication of "The Neuro-Psychoses of Defense" by Freud in (1894) and it was observed that change in these effects overall human functioning structure (Perry, Petraglia, Olson, Presniak & Metzger, 2012).

The term mechanism of defense has a history of development (Wallerstein, 1983) that visibly started with the contribution by Freud Anna (1992). Defense processes can be conscious or unconscious (Erdelyi, 2001). These are related to attribution process (Kwon & Lemon, 2000), hope (Kwon, 2002a), racial identity, attitudes (Utsey & Gernat, 2002), creativity (Domino, Short, Evans, & Romano, 2002), emotional intelligence (Pellitteri, 2002), IQ (Haan 1963: Cramer, 1999), schemas (Horowitz & Znoj, 1999), group identity (Cramer, 2004a), classification of mental health (Vaillant, 2000a), diagnosis (Porcerelli, Olson, Presniak, Markova & Miller, 2009), personality developments (cognition) (Cramer, 2003b), therapeutic alliance (Despland, de Roten, Despars, Stigler & Perry, 2001), alexithymia (Besharat, & Shahidi, 2011), gender (Petraglia, Thygesen, Lecours, & Drapeau, 2009) multicultural studies (Tori, & Bilmes, 2002), distress relief (Drapeau, De Roten, Perry & Despland, 2003), negative identity style (Berzonsky & Kinney, 2008), research orientation of dynamic nature (Lingiardi, Lonati, Delucchi, Fossati, Vanzulli & Maffei, 1999), age (Cramer, 1987c), medical education (La Cour, 2002), experience, levels of stress (Grevin, 1996) and groups (Dickinson & Ashby, 2005). Measuring ego defense mechanisms objectively is possible (Bond, 2004).

To measure mechanisms of defense with standardized tests is difficult (Haan, 1965) but the role of these in therapeutic alliance, process and understanding of these as facilitators for therapists to manage the process is known. In certain cases the frequency of the

emergence of these found related to specific symptoms (Gomes, Ceitlin, Hauck & Terra, 2008: da Silva, Pinheiro, Faria, Osório, da Silva & Botella, 2007: Ambresin, de Roten, Drapeau & Despland, 2007: Olson, Perry, Janzen, Petraglia & Presniak, 2011: Saint Martin, Valls, Rousseau, Callahan & Chabrol, 2013). Moreover, tests like Defense Style Questionnaire, The Life Style Index, Coping Inventory for Stressful Situations are available to assist as standardized measures for better psychotherapeutic relations (Saint Martin, Valls, Rousseau, Callahan & Chabrol, 2013: Hyphantis, Goulia, Floros, Iconomou, Pappas, Karaivazoglou, & Assimakopoulos, 2011). A recent neuropsychanalytic study has supported the use of standardized tests related with defense mechanism during psychotherapy (Costa & Oliveira, 2015) because somatic symptoms and defense mechanisms found to be related (Hyphantis, Taunay, Macedo, Soeiro-de-Souza, Bisol, Fountoulakis, ... & Carvalho, 2013a) and also found to influence change during the therapy (Hill, Tasca, Presniak, Francis, Palardy, Grenon, , ... & Bissada, 2015) moreover, interpreting defense mechanisms is an important technique related to psychotherapy and alliance (Gerostathos, de Roten, Berney, Despland & Ambresin, 2014).

Defense mechanisms are related with health (Malone, Cohen, Liu, Vaillant, & Waldinger 2013) and mental health and predict dynamic personality function variety (Roy, Perry, Luborsky & Banon, 2009). Defense mechanisms are important in professional situations (Laurent, Aubert, Chahraoui, Bioy, Mariage, Quenot & Capellier, 2014), professional performance (Sepidehdam, Karimi & Besharat, 2012), everyday demanding hectic professional duties (Kocijan, Gregurek and Karlovic, 2007) and professional needs (Bovey, & Hede, 2001). Laurent, Aubert, Chahraoui, Bioy, Mariage, Quenot & Capellier (2014) has reflected that defense mechanisms encompass the totality of human presence, whereas, Vaillant (2000a) highlighted the role of these regarding positive human growth?

Mechanism of defense functioning is closely related to coping (Kramer, Despland, Michel, Drapeau & de Roten, 2010) as an explanatory concept (Vaillant, Bond & Vaillant, 1986 b) that is related to adaptation (Perry & Bond, 2012a) and can influence the individuals' identity, status and mental states (Cramer 1998d: Parker, Taylor, & Bagby, 1998: Mullen, Blanco, Vaughan, Vaughan & Roose, 1999).

However, it is an overlooked area in personality research (Cramer, 1998d) besides the fact that personality and defence mechanisms are related

(Cramer, 1999) and these play a role in personality disorders (Perry, Presniak & Olson, 2013b). Moreover, defense mechanisms could help to differentiate between personality types (Presniak, Olson, Porcerelli & Dauphin, 2010). Furthermore, specific defenses predict certain specifications in personality type (Berman & McCann, 1995) and are associated with different symptoms (Offer, Lavie, Gothelf, & Apter, 2000).

Stress is a common phenomenon in human life and coping with it is related to certain crucial aspects (Saucan, Micle, Liiceanu, & Oancea, 2011). The bio and physical functioning reasons support the relationship of chronic stress with physical and mental health (Juster, McEwen & Lupien, 2010).

Stress causes health problems (Cohen, 2004) and chronic stress generates mental health symptoms, perhaps due to dendrites in the amygdala (Eiland, Ramroop, Hill, Manley & McEwen, 2012). Conformity has a role is stressful social conditions (Szolnoki & Perc, 2015) moreover; social conditions can explain abnormal social reactions (Bussu, Detotto & Sterzi, 2013) therefore studies are required to improve understanding about conformity in psychoanalytic and other fields (Allen, 1965). Stress coping and psychological defense mechanisms are closely related (Driskell & Salas, 2013). Coping is diverse in nature, so addressing its multiple aspects is a constant need (Moos & Holahan, 2003) because adaptation is the product of coping and defenses play a role in it (Kramer, 2010: Kramer, De Roten, Michel & Despland, 2009a).

Defense mechanisms in certain cases are sequential (Perry, Beck, Constantinides & Foley, 2009). It has been observed that subjects with different psychological disorders select different defense mechanisms to cope (Perry, 2001a), moreover, change in defensive function can bring in change in symptoms (Johansen, Krebs, Svartberg, Stiles & Holen, 2011) furthermore, users priorities in certain cases determine the use of defense mechanisms (Parekh, Majeed, Khan, Khan, Khalid, Khwaja, ... & Jehan, 2010) and defense styles could gradually become more adaptive with improved symptoms, however, changes in styles do predict symptoms, but not causality (Perry & Bond, 2005 b) but, defense styles are changeable and could be made more adaptive (Bond, 2004).

Startle and surprise are two commonly known human emotion expressions. Startle is an involuntarily triggered response behavior to a startling stimulus condition (Carlsen, Dakin, Chua & Franks, 2007); different species have different reactions to startle

(Hilary, Julie, Steven, Melina 2004). It is a syndrome that is consisted of three groups (Bakker, Van Dijk, van den, & Tijssen, 2006) these are controlled by amygdala (Ebner-Priemer, Badeck, Beckmann, Wagner, Feige, Weiss ... & Bohus, 2005) and serotonin pathways of genetic origin play a role in its emergence (Brocke, Armbruster, Muller, Hensch, Jacob, Lesch., ... & Strobel, 2006). Experiences contribute in startle elevation (Bryant & Guthrie, 2005) that is capable of generating negativity and positivity (Hellgren, Bannbers, Åkerud, Risbrough, & Sundström, 2012). Social conditions play a role in the development of startle (Varty, Paulus, Braff & Geyer, 2000) therefore it is used to measure social conditions because of its structural permanence (Vanman, Mejia, Dawson, Schell & Raine, 2003). Moreover startle methodology helps to assess various emotional states (Grillon, 2002) because startle has a connection with anxiety (Campbell, Gorka, McGowan, Nelson, Sarapas, Katz., ... & Shankman, 2014) however, a mix of fear and anxiety is a difficult situation to be determined with startle (Moberg & Curtin 2009). Some experiments revealed that startle influenced performance even in very critical hours (Landman, Groen, Van Paassen, Bronkhorst & Mulder, 2017). Foster & Keane (2015) observed that those events could be explained easily are less surprising than those that are more difficult to be explained. In the present study startle was achieved by asking an unusual question from the strangers by a stranger professional.

Incongruence causes surprise (Ludden, Schifferstein & Hekkert, 2012). Surprise is a state of the observer in a situation where posterior and prior beliefs about the world have a difference, or it is a "new data that renders the prevailing conceptual model invalid" (Stokes, 2001: Bredehoeft, 2005) or it is a state of lack of sufficient information about the basic dynamics confronted by the adaptive system (McDaniel Jr, Jordan & Fleeman, 2003) a credence change as adaptive learning (Baldi & Itti, 2010). Surprise has four components (Reisenzein, 2000). It is related to satisfaction (Vanhamme & Snelders, 2001: Vanhamme, 2000a) and decision process (Lempert, Popper & Bankes, 2002), therefore, its business importance is also known (Erev 2012). A surprise because of content has gained importance in a television presentation variety also (Alden, Mukherjee & Hoyer, 2000). Shock and surprise evoke defense mechanisms (Reik, 1936). In the present study surprise were achieved by asking an encouraging question from the strangers by a stranger professional.

METHOD AND PROCEDURE:

Human subjects were required to be questioned in the work; therefore Research Ethics Committee Riphah International University Sityana Road, Faisalabad Pakistan was approached for review and approval of the proposal for the conduct of the study. The committee was apprised that the experimental conditions proposed in the work so far cultural context were concerned were neither related to the privacy of an individual nor these were such those could cause any harm to the mental or physical states of the participants, it was also submitted that due to the nature of the study seeking prior written approval from the subjects was not practicable. On that the committee found that “the role of participants in the study is not of personal nature related to ‘individual identity’ or ‘concern’ as participants” therefore the committee sanctions the study and permits the conduct”.

A total numbers of 1391 responses of the same number of individuals belonging to various professions, institutions, places, gender, age, education, social status and other demographic features were collected. The respondents were medical doctors, nurses, paramedical staff, students, teachers and staff of private and public sector Universities, Colleges and Schools and staff and workers of public sector offices. 16 volunteer psychologists completing a Master of Philosophy in Psychology supervised by the co-authors were tasked to collect the data from the targeted population from the three main cities of a country experiencing war like situation. Each volunteer was tasked to reach the assigned entrance of the assigned University, College, School, Hospital or Public Sector Office well before the time of the official opening time. The researchers putting on an official coverall with a prominent nameplate (Psychologist) reached the assigned places and asked each early comer why he or she was before their duty start time? And after the starting time asked the late comers that why they were late? Since it was obligatory for all recorded (participants) to attend their workplace ‘on time’ for service or other requirements or reasons, so an unexpected question by a psychologist with a ‘psychologist’ tag it was assumed was capable of creating emotional states like ‘surprise’ in former and ‘startle’ like situations in the later cases? Each researcher while asking the given questions recorded each response or behavior of the respondent on a ‘given from’ even in case the participant refused to

answer was also recorded. However, regarding the consent requirements, after the recording of the response of the participants each participant was told by the researchers in a polite and humble tone that, “the question asked was about a research of national interest and if he or she is not feeling satisfied with his or her response and was unwilling to participate his or her response could be omitted” but none opted. In that way the oral and informed recorded consent was obtained from all participants, although that was exempted by authorizing committee. The responses of both late comers and early comers assessed in the light of defined mechanisms listed and explained by Trevithick (2011) as well as by Anna (1937) Defense Mechanism Charts and a list by Vaillant (1992c), whereas for acting out Rowan (2000) was consulted. The defense mechanism mainly considered in the study includes, acting out (AO), displacement (D), intellectualization (I), projection (P), rationalization (R.) reaction formation (RA), undoing (U) as well as all others under the title ‘others’ those were mentioned in an appendix in Vaillant (1992c). Following responses and their possible connotations from all the respondents in both cases were considered as normal, “Yes, I am late” or “Yes I am before time”. In case the respondent responded the way in which he or she tried to accuse anything or anybody else or Something that was considered as a reason to be late or in time like “Yes, I am late because of....,” “Yes, I am before time because of.....” and other similar responses were labeled as (P) in the same manner entire responses recorded and labeled as per the defined meanings of defense mechanisms as mentioned in (Vaillant, 1992c: Trevithick, 2011: Freud, 1992: Rowan, 2000).

RESULTS:

The responses of both late comers and early comers reflected a significant unanimity of focus on a few defense mechanisms in both groups, although the populations were diverse, moreover, some interesting percentages of choice also emerged like, in (I) the percentage of early comers was higher than late comers, whereas in (R.), the percentage was higher in late comers than early comers. Moreover, in (P), the percentage was higher in late comers than early comers. Furthermore, in (AO), the percentage was higher in late comers than early comers and in (RF) the percentage was higher in late comer as compared with early comers (Figure-1) and (Table-1).

The figure shows the percentage difference between early and late comer respondents, in (I) the percentage of early comer was higher than late comer respondents, whereas in (R.), the percentage was higher in late comer than early comer. Moreover,

in(P), the percentage was higher in late comer than early comer. Furthermore, in (AO), the percentage was higher in late comer than early comer. Finally, in(RF), the percentage was higher in late comer than early comer.

Table 1

DEFENSE MECHANISMS, STARTLE, SURPRISE AND COPING

Percentage Difference between Early and Late Coming respondents					
	I	R	P	AO	RF
Early Coming	49.2	15	35.5	0.3	0
Late Coming	33.7	15.7	47.2	3.1	0.2

The table shows the percentage difference between early coming and late coming respondents, in (I) the percentage of early coming was higher than late coming respondents, whereas in (R.), the percentage was higher in late coming than early coming. Moreover, in (P), the percentage was higher in late coming than early coming. Furthermore, in (AO), the percentage was higher in late coming than early coming. Finally, in (RF), the percentage was higher in late coming than early coming.

CONCLUSION AND DISCUSSION:

The findings generated a few questions like the one that how did exceptional similarity in defense mechanism as a coping choice emerged in demographically heterogeneous groups of participants with completely different backgrounds in majority of the cases? Was that a kind of collective coping or similar course of group reaction for some inner emotional state in a uniform outer situation by a may be national group and if so than how it was informing? Was that a collective response due to the situational effects on the group of the participants because, it has been reported that different group situations affect the members of a group (Barsade, 2002) and theory supports that group members' emotions can influence the group process (Fontaine, Scherer, Roesch & Ellsworth, 2007)?

In that context, it has been reported that management emotions prevail within a group (Huy, 2011) and social sharing develop when an emotional event is confronted collectively by a group (Rimé, 2007). Moreover, findings about 'Positive Group Affect Spiral', relationship with group emotion norms (Walter & Bruch 2008) have also been reported. It has also been observed that negative group emotions are transmitted within all group members (Reus & Liu, 2004) and an individual's emotions can influence the group and group reactions in the present and future (Hareli & Rafaeli, 2008). It was also reflected that

conflicts confronted by the group could affect the group emotional climate (Ayoko, Callan & Härtel, 2008).

To study individual in group in own landscape is an emerging need (Norton, 2002) to sketch human taxonomic psychological situation characteristics (Parrigon, Woo, Tay & Wang, 2017) because location of an individual can influence an individual's behavior (Oishi, 2014) even neighborhood influences behaviors (Oishi, 2015a) because situational strengths and personality strengths to work together (Dalal, Meyer, Bradshaw, Green, Kelly & Zhu, 2015) and circumstances and surroundings influence personality (Vik, Lilja & Nygård, 2007) and attitudes (Morni & Sahari 2013) as in a store, the environment of the store influences consumers (Maym & Ahmadinejad, 2011). Since environment effects on personality are possible (Zimmermann & Neyer, 2014) therefore, military situations are not an exception therefore, military situations are not an exception (Wallenius, Bäckman & Larsson, 2014) perhaps that was the reason that Zhang, Brecke, Lee, He & Zhang (2007) considered global warming as one of the causes for the outbreak of wars and war remained a persistent feature of human history although peoples are jointly working to reduce its risk (World Disasters Report, 2014) but still that is there (Joanna, 2006). The influence of war on human mind has been assessed and reviewed with reference to psychopathology suicide, anxiety, substance abuse, aggression, conflicts and other mental ailments (Bell, Méndez, Martínez, Palma & Bosch, 2012). Moreover, psychologists are committed to do something to reduce it (Pyszczynski, Solomon & Greenberg, 2003) because in war women suffer more (Murthy & Lakshminarayana, 2006). South Asia, (Wasay, Khatri & Kaul, 2014) is a nuclear rivalry zone (Javaid & Sahrai, 2016) with persistent escalation (Basrur, 2009) that is 'dangerous' (Cheema, 2015) and constant war anticipation among people of the region resemble with "collective insecurity"

(Riezler,1944) if so, how such may be bringing insocial psychopathological influence or otherwise as observed by Dr. William C. Menninger in his Presidential address (1948-49) in (Glueck, 1950)toinfluence the collective minds of the people of the region, it is an important question that came to light after the findings of the study and that hint towards the possibility of studying similar world situations with the help of group selection of defense mechanisms or ‘collective coping’? It is known that threat to self or authority creates additional security needs (Egorov & Sonin, 2011). Moreover, certainly plays a role in the emotion process (Tiedens & Linton. 2001) and consistent ‘otherness’ feel can cause tension and conflicting feels (Sfeir, 2010). Moreover, certainty is also related to risk taking behaviors (Bagneux, Bollon & Dantzer, 2012) and risk confrontation provides a basis to address ‘uncertainty’ (Renn, Klinke& Van Asselt, 2011). Uncertainty affects groups and group relationship (Hogg, 2000) and can generate adaptive responses (Hullett& Witte, 2001) and certain other behaviors to help those copes with certain uncertain human conditions (Spence, Lachlan & Burke, 2007). Therefore, the results of the study reflect clues about social adaptability promotion possibility in a war like tense national group situations and possibility of its understanding with the help of collective coping. Moreover, collective group response is informing about surrounding effects.

Studying emotions in a social context are most of the times beneficial because, specific fear is capable of influencing a nation, even global community (Mandel & Vartanian, 2010). Emotional state effect choice (Drače&Ric, 2012). Fear is an automatic emotion based on perceived present and past experiences (Bar-Tal, 2001). The different effects of fear and anger have revealed that how do the interplay of both is different in social context (Lerner, Gonzalez, Small & Fischhoff, 2003). Anger is related to decision making and its nature is different from negative emotions because of certain related components in it are those closer to positive emotions (Lerner & Tiedens, 2006a). Anger is related to perceived risks, moreover, proximity to the risk situation can cause more risk feel (Benzion, Shahrabani & Shavit, 2009). Moreover, anger and fear receive risk threats differently and emotions are important in public policy (Lerner, Gonzalez, Small & Fischhoff, 2003). Present findings could be useful to study certain effects on emotions in group behaviors with collective coping with a variety of situations even in the nuclear possibility conflict zone.

The usage of defense mechanisms as ‘collective coping’ can be used in psychology of politics as well. In comparative psychological context, it is possible to study ‘collective coping’ in the context of a pack hunting or running away behaviors for gains that remained a prime human objective in the history and present competitive century? However, psychology is capable of addressing international situations (McDermott, Wernimont & Koopman, 2011) and information can be used to understand collectivity (Brodbeck& Guillaume, 2015) provided the experts may peep into the life of selected mechanisms of defenses to further elaborate ‘collective coping’ to address basic relevant ifs and buts.

Conflict of Interest Statement: It is declared that no author of the study has any potential conflict of interest.

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